

A Novel Approach for Efficient Books Utilization in a Library Management System

Radha Krishna Jana¹, Arko Kundu², Purnendu Naskar², Hrithik Paul¹

¹ JIS University, Kolkata-700109

²The Calcutta Technical School, Kolkata-700013

Abstract— Library is a very essential resource for learning. This is an important resource for students also. There are several books in school or college library. But not available huge no. of books. In this work, we developed a novel approach for proper distribution of books. There are several parameters for books distribution.

Keyword:Library Management System, Book Distribution, Scheduling,

I. INTRODUCTION

A project that electronically maintains and retains book information in accordance with student needs is the college library management website. The technology makes it easier for the library manager and students to maintain continuous inventory of all the books that are available. It enables the learner and the administrator to look for the desired book. Colleges are forced to monitor the books they loan out, track their returns, and even determine fines. If done by hand, this operation will be time-consuming and prone to errors. By letting the system maintain track of details like the date of issue, the deadline for returning the book, and even fine information, these mistakes can be prevented and manual tracking is obviated.

A library is a collection of information sources. Similar resources have created a clear community among readers, students, and others, enabling them to more easily refer to or borrow the book. To locate books and access journals with ease, use the Library Management System Software for Library Management. By automating routine library processes, the library automation system lightens the workload for library employees. It creates the record's consistency and level of quality. The information sector grew as people's value for information increased, and

technological advancements altered library consumers' expectations. It presents the libraries with a difficulty as well as an opportunity. The most intricate tasks are managed by the integrated library system, which also gives the librarian the ability to oversee the library.

II. Literature Study

This study developed on windows based application. The user easily accesses their account and check the books status in library database. This is time consuming technique [1]. This work developed with c and Visual c++ language [2]. This is a digital library management system. This system develop using Php, html and css [3]. This approach monitoring book searching, book issues status, student information etc. This work reduces the human efforts [4]. This is a android mobile based library management system. This technique reduces physical effort and we can access required information from anywhere [5]. This is open source software for digital library management system [6]. This is digital library management system. The teacher add the lecture notes in this system [7]. This is a web based library management system. The user can access anywhere any time [8]. This is a digital tool for online library management system. This work developed using c# and Dot net technology [9].

This is a solution for managing mobile libraries. This worked developed using MySQLi database, Android Studio, HTML, PHP, and CSS [11]. This is a automated library management software. Thos work developed using VB.NET and SQL Server[12].

This worked developed on Java technology and Sql database[13]. Data mining and clustering techniques are the foundation of this library management system[14]. This is IoT-Enable RFID-Based library management system[15].

III. Proposed System

Users of this library management system will be able to access it through a login page. Only students will be able to log in on this website. Students must register using their name, registration number, roll number, library ID, and department in order to use the library's resources. Following a successful registration, they will receive login credentials and library access.

Pupils have the option to search books using the book's title alone, the author's name, or any other fields of their choosing. Following the conclusion of this procedure, pupils will receive book details and the student can add the book to the demand list. After the book is demanded, his demand list on the dashboard will be updated and an accession number of the book would be shown. After successfully borrowing the book from the library, the borrowed list will be updated. Students should notify library staff members if they lose a book so they may adjust their account and take the necessary measures, such paying a fine. The administrator can add and remove students, add books, change account

information.

IV. Proposed Algorithm

- ❖ The first and foremost step of a user to go through the system would be login to his/her account by entering username and password. If their username and password matches with the Database, then it would be a valid attempt otherwise it will be an invalid attempt. For a valid attempt the user would be allowed to go into the next step otherwise it would be obstructed.
- ❖ On the next step, the user can search the book which is required by them. The searching can be done by book title name, author name or publisher name for best and proper results. If the book is present in the book database, the book will be shown to the user. If the book is not present in the data base, the result will be an invalid search or book is not found.
- ❖ Now the book which the user required from the search results, would be selected by user and add it to the demand list as specified.
- ❖ The last and final step is the borrowing of book which would be done by following some conditions and properties as required by the system for proper

distribution of a particular book. If the book which is demanded by the user is also demanded by any other user/s then the FCFS rule will be followed. If FCFS rule gets overuled, then Library usage and history method would be followed where each user would be getting the particular book for a specific amount of time according to their library usage. When this method also get overuled, then either Library ID will be checked or the semester which the student is currently enrolled in will be given the most priority.

V. Discussion

This library management system is a well-designed system and contains proper DFD model to ensure each it would be helpful for each and every user. The DFD model is well structured and doesnot contains any faults in it. Every user would have their own privacy as the account of their own will be password protected. The books will be efficiently and properly distributed to the users which would ensure time management as well as user's need.

This system also ensures with less number of book and with more number of students we can distribute the book within a specific time to decrease wastage of time. Further modifications can be made on this system like Book damage/ loss/delay fine, Password change, Timer for each user to return the book, etc.

VI. Conclusion

Students will benefit from this website's digital version of the library management system. The entire process is done online, allowing students to look up books, request books, and check out books. Additionally, it features a student login feature that allows students to view the status of books they have been issued, request books, and contact us with suggestions. The future scope of this library system are : Forgot password feature, Profile change by user feature, Full Admin supported system, Settings modification as required.

References:

1. A.Thendral Mary, S.Ramya, Mr.S.Krishna Murthy, Dr.A.Valarmathi, Enhanced Library Management System,

International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts, Volume 5, Issue 4 October 2017.

2. Chunchao Liu, Sheng Ma, Design of Library Management System, Open Access Library Journal, Vol 5, Dec. 25, 2018.

3. Fems, Seimiekumo Solomon, Zifawei O. Kennedy, George Deinbofa, Oberhiri Oruma Godwin, Design And Implementation Of Digital Library Management System. A Case Study Of The Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State, International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Volume 9, Issue 12, December 2019.

4. Gatete Marcel, UWIZEYIMANA Faustin, Development of an Online Integrated Library Management Information System: Case Study "University of Gitwe, International Journal of Scientific Research in Computer Science and Engineering, Vol,8, Issue.2, pp.65-76, April (2020).

5. Dr. P. G. Kuppusamy¹, D. Mounika², N. Jhansi Chowdary³, V. Jahnvi Reddy⁴, N. Mohan⁵, K. Mahesh Reddy⁶, Design and Implement an Android Mobile Library Management System, The International journal of analytical and experimental modal analysis, Volume XII, Issue VI, June/2020.

6. Muslim Aswari, Muhammad Kristiawan, Happy Fitria, Senayan Library Management System Application as Digital Library Management, International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies, Vol. 20 No. 2 May 2020, pp. 129-136.

7. Shubham Zunjar, Rahul Yadav, Rutuja Markad, Sneha Patil, LIBRARY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM, International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology, Volume: 07 Issue: 03 | Mar 2020.

8. Tsega Weldu Araya, Ass. Pro. Adhana Mengsteab, Designing Web-based Library Management System, International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology, Vol. 9 Issue 10, October-2020.

9. Shanmugam A.P, Ramalakshmi, A, Sasthri, G Baalachandran, S, Library Management System, Journal of Xi'an University of Architecture & Technology, Volume XII, Issue XI, 2020.

Journal of Computer Science and Engineering in Innovations and Research (JCSEIR)

Research Paper

Vol.-1, Issue- 1, July 2024

ISSN: ISSN: 3049-1762 (Online)

10. Dr.S.S. Aravinth, Aiswarya.S, Amin Tuni Gure, Durga Prasad Sharma, Nitish Kumar Choudhary, Naveen P, A Survey On Online Library Management Systems And Internet Reference Accessing Portal Using Online Learning Agents, International Journal of Aquatic Science, ISSN: 2008-8019, Vol 12, Issue 02, 2021.

11. Ndukwe Oke Eke , Ibrahim Anka Salihu , Design and Implementation of a Mobile Library Management System for Improving Service Delivery, Traektoriâ Nauki = Path of Science. 2021. Vol. 7. No 4.

12. Priyadharshini J., Priyadharshin U., Mrs Beulaprincess, LIBRARY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM, GALAXY INTERNATIONAL INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL (GIIRJ) ISSN (E): 2347-6915 Vol. 10, Issue 8, Aug. (2022).

13. Sourabh Sharma¹ , Sunny Mishra² , Shubham Gupta³ , Sachin Kumar⁴, Library Management System, International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology, Volume 10 Issue V May 2022.

14. Lu Pang, Library Management System Based on Data Mining and Clustering Algorithm, Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing Volume 2022.

15. MAITHILI ANDHARE, KISHOR BHANGALE, VIJAYALAXMI S. KUMBHAR, ARTI TEKADE, SUYASH CHOUDHARI, AJINKYA DESHPANDE & SANKET CHAVAN , iot-enabled rfid-based library management and automatic book recommendation system using collaborative learning, sentiment analysis and deep learning, PROCEEDINGS OF ICSADL 2022, PP 753–765.

Authors Profile

Author Arko Kundu, The Calcutta Technical School, Kolkata

Author Purnendu Naskar, The Calcutta Technical School, Kolkata

Author Radha Krishna Jana, JIS University, Kolkata